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MALOLETNIČKE KRIVIČNE SANKCIJE U PRAKSI: KO, KOGA, OD ČEGA I KAKO ŠTITI?

Zakon o maloletnim učiniocima krivičnih dela i krivičnopravnoj zaštiti maloletnih lica – sam naslov zakona otkriva mnogo o njegovom duhu. Ovim zakonom maloletnici se štite kao posebna kategorija žrtava, ali se istovremeno obezbeđuje i njihova zaštita u svojstvu učinilaca — zaštita od represivnog karaktera državnog aparata, sa ciljem da se u potpunosti otklone faktori koji dovode do njihovog prestupničkog ponašanja. Taj cilj treba postići pružanjem zaštite i pomoći, kao i obezbeđivanjem opšteg i specijalizovanog obrazovanja i vaspitanja maloletnih učinilaca. Ceo sistem usmeren je ka podsticanju razvoja i jačanju lične odgovornosti maloletnika i ka pravilnom razvoju njegove ličnosti — a sve radi njegove uspešne reintegracije u društvenu zajednicu. Srpsko krivično pravo ne kažnjava maloletnike. Ipak, kada ga sankcioniše, srpski pravosudni sistem štiti maloletnika – od njega samog, loših spoljnih uticaja koji ga „kvare“ i podstiču njegovo delinkventno i protivpravno ponašanje, štiti ga od sopstvene represivnosti, zatim od faktičke, čak i terminološke stigmatizacije u toku postupka i sprovođenja sankcija (jer zakonodavac je veoma izričit i precizan u upotrebi bitno različitih izraza u maloletničkom krivičnom pravu), i konačno štiti ga od samog procesa, predviđajući diverzione mehanizme i mere. U svemu ovome se ogleda ili bi barem trebalo da se ogleda svrha maloletničkih krivičnih sankcija i maloletničkog krivičnog prava. Da li je to u praksi zaista tako? Štiti li, popravlja li, vaspitava li domaći sistem maloletne prestupnike? Sistem ima mehanizme za postizanje samoproklamovane svrhe, a da li ih koristi i kako – biće predmet ovog rada. Cilj je ovog rada da kroz ilustraciju i analizu višegodišnje prakse Višeg suda u Nišu da odgovore na pitanja ko, koga, od čega i kako štiti u srpskom maloletničkom krivičnom pravu.

Ključne reči: maloletničke krivične sankcije, svrha krivičnih sankcija, maloletni učinioci krivičnih dela, zaštita maloletnika u krivičnom postupku.

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JUVENILE CRIMINAL SANCTIONS IN PRACTICE: WHO PROTECTS WHOM, FROM WHAT, AND HOW?

The title of the Act on Juvenile Offenders and Criminal-Law Protection of Juveniles (hereinafter: the Juvenile Justice Act) reveals the spirit and the key facets of this legislative act. The Juvenile Justice Act protects minors as a special category of victims but also safeguards minors as offenders, shielding them from the repressive nature of the state apparatus for the purpose of fully eliminating the factors that trigger the minors' delinquent conducts. This aim is to be achieved by providing protection and assistance, and ensuring general and subject-specific education of minor delinquents. The entire system aims to foster the proper development of minors' personality, strengthen their personal responsibility, and provide necessary support for their reintegration into the social community. Serbian criminal law does not punish minors. Yet, when it imposes sanctions, the Serbian judicial system seeks to protect the minors from themselves, from harmful external influences that "corrupt" and incite delinquent and unlawful behavior, from the repressive tendencies of the system itself, from factual and even terminological stigmatization during the proceedings and execution of sanctions (considering that the legislator is explicit and precise in using significantly different terms within juvenile criminal law), as well as from the process itself, by providing for diverse mechanisms and measures. All these safeguards reflect, or at least should reflect, the true purpose of juvenile criminal sanctions and juvenile criminal law. However, is this truly the case in practice? Does the Serbian juvenile criminal law system protect, correct, and educate juvenile offenders? The system comprises mechanisms aimed at achieving the proclaimed aims, but are they actually used? This paper examines whether and how these mechanisms are employed in practice. The purpose of the paper is to illustrate and analyze the judicial practice of the Higher Court in Niš in the past few years in order to provide answers to the questions who protects whom, from what, and how within the Serbian juvenile criminal law framework.

Keywords: juvenile criminal sanctions, purpose of criminal sanctions, juvenile offenders, protection of minors in criminal proceedings.